

New Species of *Compsogusa* Schwarz, 2021 from the Philippines

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Abstract. 1. New species of *Compsogusa* Schwarz, 2021 from Luzon is described. 2. Collection record of *Compsogusa* from Mindanao is discussed. 3. Species key and known distribution map of *Compsogusa* species is presented.

Compsogusa was established by Schwarz in 2021 to include a new species, *rheae*, that he described from his extensive natural history observations and quality photographs while conducting field work in Panay Island. The genus description of *Compsogusa* and the species treatment of *rheae* included below is sourced directly from Schwarz' 2021 paper. At the time of his publication, Schwarz noted the existence of a second undescribed species of *Compsogusa* from the Bicol region of Luzon that was in the possession of the present author. This new species is herein described as *Compsogusa luzoni* **n. sp.** An additional male specimen of *Compsogusa*, thought to possibly represent a third species, has since been discovered from the Caraga region of Mindanao and is also reviewed. Both *Compsogusa* specimens were collected by BLumawig and his team in the Philippines on commission of the present author and are deposited within the author's private collection.

Discussion. In Schwarz' 2021 paper that documented three new species of Mantodea from Panay Island, he wrote that "*Compsogusa*, while related to the Sundaian and Philippine genus *Compsomantis* Saussure, 1872, has evolved into a bark mantis ecotype common in the Afro- and Neotropics, but not found in the southern Philippines, or in the Sunda archipelago, for that matter". In July 2021, a few months after Schwarz' publication, a male specimen of *Compsogusa* was collected in the southern Philippine island of Mindanao, thereby immediately extending the known range of this genus away from the Western Visayas and apart from the aforementioned collection record of the undescribed species from Luzon.

The abdominal terminalia of the male Mindanao specimen were removed and sent to Evgeny Shcherbakov for analysis. Shcherbakov extracted, prepared, photographed and analyzed the genitalia of this sample. The results of this analysis indicated that the male genitalia of the Mindanao specimen were identical to the male genitalia pictured in Schwarz' original description of *rheae*. Shcherbakov discussed his findings with the present author and noted that the genitalic

similarity between the holotype and the Mindanao specimen was not in itself an argument against species distinction, provided that there were external differences between the two specimens that were more sizeable.

Morphometric data of the Mindanao specimen was compiled by the present author and compared with those published for *rheae* within Schwarz' original description. The results of this latter analysis provided only one quantitative measure of significant difference. In *rheae*, the pronotum length to forecoxae length is 1.22. This same measure is 1.43 in the Mindanao specimen. There was only one qualitative difference found between the two specimens. The exterior surface of male *rheae* forelegs have a dark brown overcast, rendering their surface color dark reddish-brown to blackish overall, obscuring the irregular bands. The forelegs of the Mindanao specimen are without a dark brown overcast, making the irregular bands evident. However, this pigmentation difference could be considered within the realm of intraspecific polychromatic variation, thus leaving the shortened pronotal length of the Mindanao specimen the only character of significance.

Given that there has only been one specimen of *Compsogusa* from Mindanao recorded, which has very similar morphometrics to *rheae* and identical genitalia to this type species, there is not yet enough evidence to determine with confidence that there is a distinct species that inhabits the southern Philippines. However, the pronotum:forecoxae measure is quite significant and the collection locale of Mindanao island is highly suggestive of evolutionary modification or adaptive radiation of a colonizing species. For these reasons, it is suggested that the Mindanao specimen be referred to as *Compsogusa* **aff.** *rheae*, i.e. this specimen has some affinity to *rheae* but it is not identical to it and it may belong to a new species.

Pronotum Morphometry. PL = pronotum length, measured from posterior to anterior margin. DW = supracoxal dilation width, measured from the outermost margins of the expansion. MW = minimal metazonal width, measuring from the narrowest constriction of the metazona. ZL = prozona length, measured from anterior margin of pronotum to supracoxal sulcus. ML = metazona length, measured from supracoxal sulcus to posterior margin of pronotum. The pronotal length value (PL) divided by the supracoxal dilation width value (DW) will generate the PL:DW ratio. The pronotal length value (PL) divided by the minimal metazonal width value (MW) will generate the PL:MW ratio. The metazona length value (ML) divided by the prozona length value (ZL) will generate the ML:ZL ratio. The supracoxal dilation width value (DW) divided by the minimal metazonal width value (MW) will generate the DW:MW ratio. All measurements are expressed to the nearest one hundredth. Illustration of pronotum example used above is of *Bistanta* Anderson, 2018.

Description. Habitus of small size, somewhat flattened dorsoventrally. Sexual dimorphism marked; female significantly larger and more robust. Pigmentation of both sexes tan to greenish-brown, variably mottled with reddish-brown, dark brown and black, mimicking tree bark coloration. Male with overall darker coloration and mottling.

Head capsule wider than long. Male vertex flat, positioned lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes; female vertex slightly convex, rising just above compound eyes. Ocelli quite small in both sexes, significantly more reduced in females. Lower frons transverse, narrow, superior margin broadly arched in middle. Juxtaocular bulges slightly protrude in female, much less so in male. Compound eyes prominent, positioned slightly forward, nearly spherical in male, rounded oval in female. Antennae long, filamentous, unicolorous. Pigmentation of head capsule greenish-brown, mottled with darker brown. Lower frons marked with dark brown band, extending into compound eyes.

Pronotum robust, measuring longer than forecoxae, finely keeled with marked supracoxal dilation. Pronotal surface smooth, margins with fine denticulation throughout, stouter in female. Prozonal margins gradually converge, anterior margin broadly rounded, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Metazona measures 1.6-1.9 times as long as prozona. Pronotal pigmentation greenish-brown with darker brown mottling.

Prothoracic legs moderately robust. Forecoxae significantly extending past posterior margin of metazona, apical lobes divergent. Anteroventral margin of forecoxae unarmed in male, sparsely tuberculate in female. Forefemora somewhat widened proximally, narrowing distally, armed with 4 posteroventral, 4 discoidal, 14-16 anteroventral spines; dorsal margin finely serrated. Posteroventral spines with blackish tips, separated by denticulation. Anteroventral spines nearly entirely blackish. Tibial spur groove placed in proximal fourth of forefemora. Foretibiae armed with 9-10 posteroventral and 11-12 anteroventral spines, spinal rows predominantly increasing in length before terminating in spur.

Meso/metathoracic legs long, sprawling. Femora thickened at base, narrowing distally, colored greenish-brown with three irregular, darker brown annulations. Tibiae slender throughout, colored greenish-brown with three darker brown annulations. Basitarsi of metathoracic tibiae approximately equal in length to remaining tarsomeres combined.

Wings shortened in both sexes. Male wings reach abdominal tergite VI; female wings reach tergite V-VI. Costal area narrow, apices rounded. Discoidal area opaque reddish-brown with small patches of darker brown mottling in female, greenish and brown mottling in male. Stigma indistinct, narrow. Hindwings semi-opaque with discoidal area and base of anal area yellowish to reddish-brown, anal area and apices blackish.

Abdomen of male cylindrical, female abdomen fusiform. Supra-anal plate broadly triangular with rounded apex. Cerci moderately lengthened, surpassing subgenital plate, cylindrical-tapered. Tergites II-VI gloss brown, VII-IX mottled greenish-brown. Sternites pale brownish with concentration of small, darker spots.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* are amorphous, taking on the contours of their surrounding substrate. They measure 9-13 mm long. External wall colored golden-brown. *Oothecae* are attached along ventral surface and oviposited into crevices of tree bark or inside desiccated leaves.

Development. Nymphs strongly resemble adults in form and behavior. Pigmentation of nymphs range from mottled brown to mottled green. Early instar nymphs have darkened forelegs as in adult males but temporarily lose this coloration in mid-late instars.

Adulthood. Adults can be found year round within sunlit forest edges of rainforests. Females are more commonly encountered than males and are seemingly more abundant.

Ethology. This species dwells on tree trunks throughout its entire life cycle, where they prey upon invertebrates that they encounter crawling atop the bark. Individuals orient facing upside down toward the ground to intercept other insects that ascend up the tree. Individuals demonstrate waving movements of their forelegs while navigating through and exploring their surroundings. No deimatic display is employed upon encountering danger. Threatened individuals will scuttle out of sight to the opposite side of the tree trunk or rapidly dart up the tree to avoid persistent threats.

Type Species: *Compsogusa rheae* Schwarz, 2021

Species Checklist:

- *Compsogusa luzoni* n. sp.
- *Compsogusa rheae* Schwarz, 2021

Key to *Compsogusa* Males:

- 1 Habitus larger and more elongate; body length 21-22 mm, forewing length 11.5-12 mm. Pronotum long in relation to forecoxae; pronotum length to forecoxae length 1.22. Exterior surface of forelegs with dark brown overcast, rendering surface color dark reddish-brown to blackish overall, obscuring irregular bands. Precinctive to Panay Island *C. rheae*
- 1' Habitus smaller and more compact; body length 19 mm, forewing length 10 mm. Pronotum short in relation to forecoxae; pronotum length to forecoxae length 1.43. Exterior surface of forelegs without dark brown overcast, irregular bands evident. Precinctive to Mindanao Island *C. aff. rheae*

Male *luzoni* unknown.

Key to *Compsogusa* Females:

- 1 Habitus smaller in every aspect, body length 28.5-31.5 mm, forewing length 13.5-14 mm. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.18. Forewing length to pronotal length 2.05. Precinctive to Panay Island *C. rheae*
- 1' Habitus larger in every aspect, body length 35 mm, forewing length 17 mm. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 1.87. Forewing length to pronotal length 2.21. Precinctive to Luzon Island *C. luzoni* n. sp.

Female *aff. rheae* unknown.

Figure Plate 1. Distribution range map of *Compsogusa*

	<i>C. luzoni</i>	<i>C. rheae</i>	<i>C. aff. rheae</i>
PHILIPPINES			
Balabac			
Basilan			
Biliran			
Bohol			
Burias			
Busuanga			
Calayan			
Camiguin			
Catanduanes			
Cebu			
Culion			
Dinagat			
Dumaran			
Guimaras			
Jolo			
Leyte			
Luzon	X		
Marinduque			
Masbate			
Mindanao			X
Mindoro			
Negros			
Palawan			
Panay		X	
Polillo			
Samal			
Samar			
Siargao			
Sibutu			
Sibuyan			
Siquijor			
Tablas			
Tawitawi			
Ticao			

Figure Plate 2. Occurrence of different *Compsogusa* species in the main islands of the Philippines

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Compsogusa luzoni*: A, female holotype dorsal habitus; B, female holotype ventral habitus. Lagonoy, Camarines Sur Province, Bicol Region, Luzon Island, PHILIPPINES 11.2018

Compsogusa luzoni n. sp.

Description. Exterior surface of forecoxae pigmented greenish-tan, sparsely maculated with small, blackish flecks. Interior surface pale green with submarginal row of small tubercles, largest colored black. Forefemora colored light green with three faint irregular bands of black on external surface, overlapping median row of blackish spots. Internal surface pale greenish with one long, blackish dash along extreme posterior margin. Femoral brush with underlying blackish dash and additional blackish dash toward distal apex. Foretibiae pigmented greenish-brown with three irregular blackish bands on external surface. Internal surface colored pale greenish with black blotch near middle of anteroventral spinal row margin. Exterior surface of basitarsi greenish with black tip, interior surface greenish with median black stripe. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 1.87, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 2.81, metazona length to prozona length 1.83, supracoxal dilation width to minimal metazonal width 1.50. Forefemora length to pronotal length 1.16, head width to supracoxal dilation width 1.69, forewing length to pronotal length 2.21. According to present knowledge, this species is precinctive to Luzon Island in the Philippines. Male unknown.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Female*. Body length 35; pronotum length 7.5; forewing length 17; prothoracic coxa length 5.5; prothoracic femur length 8.5; metathoracic femur length 9.

Etymology. “luzoni” denotes of/from Luzon, the type location of this new species.

Material Examined. Type Specimen: Holotype. 1 ♀ Lagonoy, Camarines Sur Province, Bicol Region, Luzon Island, PHILIPPINES 11.2018, BLumawig leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Compsogusa rhae Schwarz, 2021

Diagnosis. Exterior surface of forecoxae pigmented greenish-brown in both sexes, marked with three broken bands of blackish blotches, overcast with darker brown in male. Interior surface of female forecoxae pale green with submarginal row of small tubercles, largest colored reddish-pink. Interior surface of male forecoxae light reddish-brown. Forefemora colored light green with three irregular bands of black on external surface, overlapping median row of blackish spots. Band delineation more obscured in male, with dark brown overcast, rendering surface color dark reddish-brown to blackish overall. Internal surface of forefemora pale greenish in female with three long, blackish dashes along extreme posterior margin and broken black line along median. Femoral brush with underlying blackish dash and additional faded dash toward distal apex of femora. Internal surface largely gloss black in male, fading to reddish-brown toward distal apex. Foretibiae pigmented greenish-brown with three irregular blackish bands on external surface in both sexes, overcast with dark brown in male. Internal surface colored pale greenish in female with faint traces of darker annulations, colored dark reddish-brown throughout in male with darkened annulations. Exterior surface of basitarsi blackish in female, interior surface greenish with median black stripe. Basitarsi nearly entirely blackish in male throughout. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.21, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.07, metazona length to prozona length 1.64, supracoxal dilation width to minimal metazonal width 1.39. Forefemora length to pronotal length 1.01, head width to supracoxal dilation width 1.84, forewing length to pronotal length 2.16. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.18, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.08, metazona length to prozona length 1.82, supracoxal dilation width to minimal metazonal width 1.41. Forefemora length to pronotal length 1.00, head width to supracoxal dilation width 1.85, forewing length to pronotal length 2.05. According to present knowledge, this species is precinctive to Panay Island, Philippines.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 21-22; pronotum length 5.5; forewing length 11.5-12; prothoracic coxa length 4.5; prothoracic femur length 6; metathoracic femur length 7-7.5. *Female.* Body length 28.5-31.5; pronotum length 6.5-7; forewing length 13.5-14; prothoracic coxa length 5.5; prothoracic femur length 7-7.5; metathoracic femur length 8-8.5.

Material Examined.

Type Specimens: The holotype male and allotype female of *rhae* from Panay Island, Philippines are deposited at the Philippine National Museum in Manila. These specimens have been digitized by Schwarz and the images were made available within the author's 2021 paper that detailed the original description of the species.

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Compsogusa aff. rheae*: A, male dorsal habitus; B, male ventral habitus. Esperanza, Agusan del Sur Province, Caraga Region, Mindanao Island, PHILIPPINES 07.2021

Compsogusa aff. rheae

Description. Exterior surface of forecoxae pigmented greenish-brown, marked with three broken bands of blackish blotches. Interior surface colored light reddish-brown. Forefemora colored light green with three irregular bands of black on external surface, overlapping median row of blackish spots. Internal surface largely gloss black, fading to reddish-brown toward distal apex. Foretibiae pigmented greenish-brown with three irregular blackish bands on external surface. Internal surface colored dark reddish-brown throughout with darkened annulations. Basitarsi nearly entirely blackish throughout. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.15, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.07, metazona length to prozona length 1.86, supracoxal dilation width to minimal metazonal width 1.43. Forefemora length to pronotal length 1.06, head width to supracoxal dilation width 1.89, forewing length to pronotal length 2.12. According to present knowledge, this species is precinctive to Mindanao Island in the Philippines. Female unknown.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male*. Body length 19; pronotum length 5; forewing length 10; prothoracic coxa length 3.5; prothoracic femur length 5; metathoracic femur length 6.

Material Examined. Pinned Specimen: 1 ♂ Esperanza, Agusan del Sur Province, Caraga Region, Mindanao Island, PHILIPPINES 07.2021, BLumawig leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Figure Plate 3. *Compsogusa* aff. *rheae* ♂ terminalia: A, supraanal plate and cerci; B, subgenital plate; C, genitalia dorsal aspect; D, genitalia ventral aspect. Genitalia preparation and photography by Shcherbakov.

Figure Plate 4. *Compsogusa aff. rheae* ♂ genitalia outlines. Illustration by Shcherbakov.

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References.

SCHWARZ, C. (2021): Three New Praying Mantises from Panay Island, Philippines. – Integrative Systematics: Stuttgart Contributions to Natural History, 2 (1): 35-56.

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